

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 08.02.2026
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.03.2026
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 13 (129),570-576

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.19360561

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Housing Types in the Old Gediz Town

Eski Gediz Beldesinde Mesken Tipleri

ABSTRACT

The town of Eskigediz is located in the Inner West Anatolia section of the Aegean Region. Administratively, it is attached to the province of Kütahya. The town is situated approximately 91 km from the Kütahya city center and 7 km from the Gediz district. The research area of the study is in a region that has been under the sovereignty of various civilizations since historical times. In terms of settlement characteristics, the town has frequently been exposed to flood disasters throughout history due to its location on the edge of a valley. Moreover, geologically, it lies within a seismic zone. Consequently, earthquakes of varying magnitudes occurred in the region until 1970, causing loss of life and property. During the most recent major earthquake in 1970, severe damage was inflicted upon the houses, rendering many uninhabitable, further exacerbated by subsequent fires. Following a decision by the Council of Ministers in 1970, the district of Eski Gediz was relocated 7 km to the south and re-established as a new district named Gediz. The two-story wooden residences in the town of Eskigediz, which bear traces of numerous civilizations, were placed under protection in 2001. The vast majority of the dwellings in the study area comprise wooden houses. While some of these wooden dwellings have been restored, there is a need for the restoration of the remaining structures. It has been observed that the town of Eskigediz holds tourism potential through the promotion of these dwellings, which reflect the civil architectural characteristics of the Ottoman civilization, and through the development of pension (guesthouse) activities. Another type of dwelling found in the area consists of modern, generally two or three-story houses, which were built in limited numbers after the earthquakes using entirely contemporary building materials.

Keywords: Eski Gediz, Dwelling Types, Wooden, Modern.

ÖZET

Eski Gediz beldesi, Ege Bölgesinin İç Batı Anadolu bölümünde yer almaktadır. İdari bakımdan Kütahya iline bağlıdır. Kütahya il merkezine 91 km. Gediz ilçesine 7 km. kadar uzaklıkta yer almaktadır. Araştırma sahası tarihi dönemlerden beri çeşitli medeniyetlerin hükümran olduğu bir alanda kurulmuştur. Yerleşim özellikleri açısından vadi kenarına kurulmuş olmasından ötürü, geçmişten beri sık sık sel felaketlerine maruz kalmıştır. Dahası jeolojik açıdan, bir deprem sahasıdır. Bu nedenle yörede, 1970 yılına kadar çeşitli büyüklüklerde depremler meydana gelmiş can ve mal kayıplarına neden olmuştur. En son 1970 depremi sırasında evlerde büyük hasarlar meydana gelmiş, çoğu evlerde yangının da etkisiyle kullanılamaz duruma gelmiştir. Bakanlar Kurulu'nun 1970 yılında aldığı karar sonucunda Eski Gediz ilçesi 7 km. güneyine, Gediz adıyla yeni bir ilçe olarak kurulmuştur. Eski Gediz beldesinde birçok medeniyetin izlerini taşıyan iki katlı ahşap konutlar, 2001 yılında koruma altına alınmıştır. Sahada bulunan meskenlerin büyük çoğunluğu da ahşap konutlardan oluşmaktadır. Bir kısmı restore edilen ahşap meskenlerin, geri kalanlarının da restorasyonunun gerçekleştirilmesine ihtiyaç duyulmaktadır. Eski Gediz beldesinin, Osmanlı medeniyetinin de izler taşıyan sivil mimari özelliklerini taşıyan bu meskenlerin, tanıtımlarının yapılması, pansiyonculuk faaliyetlerinin gerçekleştirilmesi sayesinde turizme konu olabilecek bir yöre olduğu görülmüştür. Saha da yer alan bir diğer mesken tipini, depremden sonra çok az sayıda inşa edilmiş tamamen çağdaş yapı malzemelerinin kullanıldığı genellikle iki veya üç katlı modern konutlar oluşturur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Eski Gediz, Mesken Tipleri, Ahşap, Modern.

1. INTRODUCTION

Administratively, the town of Eski Gediz is attached to the Gediz district of Kütahya province. Located in the Inner West Anatolia section of the Aegean region, the town is situated 91 km from the Kütahya city center and 7 km from Gediz. In terms of its mathematical location, the research area is geographically situated at 39°20' N latitude and 29°50' E longitude. The region is bordered by the province of Uşak to the south, the districts of Şaphane and Pazarlar to the west and the districts of Altıntaş and Aslanpaşa to the east, as well as the districts of Hisarcık and Çavdarhisar to the north (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location Map of the Research Area

The area possesses a very old settlement history. Various studies indicate that the first inhabitants of the region were the Phrygians (Kurt, 2024; Varlık, 2026). Later, the Roman, Seljuk, Germiyanid (*Germiyanogulları*), and Ottoman civilizations ruled the region. Many civilizations, ranging from the Phrygians to the Ottomans, have left their own traces in the field (Kızıltoprak, 2025). Located within a narrow valley, the town has witnessed disasters such as fire, flood, and earthquake in recent periods (Table 1).

Table 1. Disasters in Gediz from the Past to the Present (1852-1970)

Major Historical Events and Disasters in Gediz

Date	Event / Disaster
1852	Locust Plague (Infestation)
1875	Great Gediz Flood
1877-78	Ottoman-Russian War
1886	Earthquake
1896	Earthquake
1901	Gediz Flood
1905	Cholera Epidemic
1911	Typhoid and Whooping Cough Epidemic
1911	Gediz Flood
1912	Balkan War
1912-1915	Locust Plague (Infestation)
1913	Cholera Epidemic
1914-1918	World War I
1918	Great Gediz Fire
1919	Occupation of Gediz
1920	Battle of Gediz
1920	2nd Occupation of Gediz
1921	3rd Occupation of Gediz
1945	Gediz Flood
1970	Gediz Earthquake

Source: (Pınar, 2017)

Most recently, on March 28, 1970, an earthquake with a magnitude of 7.2 occurred. Özav (2014) stated that the town of Eski Gediz is located in an area where active fault lines are found. As a result of this, the people of Eski Gediz migrated to a large extent to the new Gediz, situated 7 km to the west. Over time, families living in surrounding villages, in particular, began to migrate to the town due to the affordability of the surviving dwellings. The vast majority of the families currently residing in Eski Gediz have migrated from the nearby villages. Indeed, the great majority of the families residing in the town consist of families who have migrated from surrounding villages. According to Çoban (2007), Many families from the villages of Akkaya, Cebrail, Akçaalan, Yaylaköy, Çukürören, Polatköy, Işıklar, Yunuslar, Kıranköy, and Yenigüney of the Gediz district migrated to Eski Gediz, which the people of Gediz had to abandon, starting from 1972. The research area, previously attached to Gediz, subsequently gained the status of an independent town municipality in 1970.

The vast majority of the houses in Eski Gediz that survived the earthquake consist of wooden houses bearing traces of the Ottoman civilization. Although some of these houses were destroyed, renovation works have been initiated by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism for the surviving ones, as the town is included in the Union of Historical Towns.

2. SETTLEMENT CHARACTERISTICS

Since the town of Eski Gediz was established in a narrow valley, it was built along the edges of the Eski Gediz valley in its northern section. According to Ürer (2013), the settlement area of Eskigediz is geographically established upon a valley oriented in a north-south direction. Gediz River, flowing through the valley bed, divides the settlement area into two. The focal point of the settlement is the eastern bank, where the slope is relatively lower (Figure 2). Development activities carried out on the north-south axis in recent years have caused the settlement to shift towards these areas, which are relatively flatter (Çoban, 2007).

Figure 2. Topographic Map of the Old Gediz Municipality

It has been observed that the settlements in the research area are generally found at elevations of 800-1100 m. The main part of the town is located on the edge of a rift valley (Figure 3). The rift valley consists mainly of volcanic rock. During the Gediz earthquake in 1970, the houses on the edge of the valley suffered less damage because the ground was made of durable materials. Considering the relatively low elevation of the location of the residences and their proximity to the rivers and streams that pass through, they serve as evidence of past flood disasters. For this reason, in order to address the risk of flooding that could occur in the town, the “Gediz River Flood Protection Project” was implemented by the State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) in 2006.

Figure 3. General View of the Research Area

The fact that our country has a high average elevation and that four seasons are distinctly felt throughout the year has rendered the construction of dwellings virtually essential for humans. The factors influencing the construction of dwellings are not limited to the effects of the natural environment such as topography and relief, additionally, the distance of the supplied material and its suitability are of great importance. Indeed, wood (timber) has been used as the building material in most of the dwellings located in the field. When other factors creating dwellings are also taken into consideration (customs and traditions, suitability of economic conditions), they carry great importance in the formation of this type of house. In terms of these aspects, there are certain differences among the constructed dwellings regarding their similarity to one another. Therefore, we analyzed dwelling types from various aspects.

Regarding dwellings constructed in the traditional structure; when the proximity of the research area to forest areas is taken into account, it has been observed that wooden dwellings are widespread. This situation, on the other hand, resulted in loss of life due to the fires caused by the stoves during the 1970 earthquake. As for modern-type residences, they are made of brick, cement, iron, and tile in terms of construction material.

The aim of this study is to reveal the characteristics of the dwelling types found in the field. In a broader sense, it is to introduce the mansion-type (konak) dwelling exhibiting traditional civil architectural characteristics and, by taking all of them under protection, to demonstrate that the region is at a level capable of hosting tourism.

2.1. Historical Development of the Town

Eski Gediz is a town where many civilizations have held sovereignty from the past to the present. Consequently, it has been referred to by various names up to the present day. Indeed, it has maintained its existence until today by bearing the name "Kadoi" during the Phrygian period, "Cadi" and "Gedos" during the Roman period, and "Gedus" under the sovereignty of the Ottoman State (Sezen, 2017).

In addition to bearing the traces of many civilizations, the town has been exposed to disasters such as earthquakes, floods, and epidemics in recent periods. It is also understood that the region witnessed many years of war in the recent past.

Following the earthquake of March 1970, which caused the relocation of the town, Eski Gediz was moved 7 km to the south under the name "Gediz" in line with the decision of the Council of Ministers. Tuncel (1977) stated that evaluating the town in the category of cities relocated as a result of natural disasters, it was moved to the locality named Karılar Pazarı on the Gediz-Uşak road (4).

3. MAIN DWELLING TYPES

The fact that the research area has been under the sovereignty of various civilizations throughout history has played a significant role in the formation of the current traditional architecture. Consequently, dwellings that were once predominantly shaped during the Ottoman period—characterized by a ground floor constructed from stone and adobe materials and an upper floor consisting of wood—are frequently observed. These structures are considered some of the finest examples of the practical utilization of natural resources in the field. The other type of dwelling consists of modern housing units constructed primarily from contemporary materials. The town's membership in the Union of Historical Towns has ensured that the number of modern dwellings remains quite limited (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Dwelling Types and Numbers, Municipality of Eski Gediz

3.1. Traditional Type Dwellings

According to Doğanay (2019), the houses that are constructed entirely from this building material, where tree trunks (or thick branches) are used in very high proportions in various forms such as boards, posts, shingles (*hartama*), rafters, and planks, processed only minimally, are called wooden dwellings.

In the research area, "Baghdadi Style" (timber frame with infill) dwellings, formed by filling the spaces between posts constructed in a wooden carcass structure with stone, gravel, and brick, are widespread (Figure 5). Furthermore, the fact that the area has been taken under protection has prevented illegal construction as well.

Of the 1,500 wooden houses identified today, 111 have been registered and restored, and restoration work needs to begin on the remaining houses.

Figure 5. A Baghdadi-Style House Located in the Research Area

Figure 6. Conservation Zoning Plan for the Old Gediz Settlement (Drawn as a Draft)

Source: (Eski Gediz Municipality)

In the area, "Baghdadi Style" houses are generally widespread. Traditional dwellings are generally constructed as two-story structures. Local names are used for certain sections of the dwellings. Indeed, the use of terms such as "hamamlık" (bathing cubicle) instead of bathroom, "yazlık" (living room) instead of salon, and "harani" (window) for window is quite common,

The high flammability of wooden dwellings, which caused significant loss of life and property during the earthquake that occurred in the region in 1970, led to fires that affected the region even more severely than the earthquake itself. According to Grabert (1971), the damage caused by the earthquake was further increased by fires resulting from overturned stoves. According to Tolun Denker (1977), although wooden houses are preferred due to their insulation against heat and humidity, their resistance to earthquakes, and ease of construction, their major drawback is the risk of fire.

It has been observed that there are numerous houses in the area resembling the mansion type (*konak*), which best reflect the typical examples of Ottoman architecture (Figure 7a). Moreover, these types of dwellings possess an internal staircase system where wood is used entirely (Figure 7b). In particular, while Kurtuluş is the first settlement neighborhood of the town; the widespread observation of mansion-type dwellings in the Hisar, İsmetpaşa, and Camikebir neighborhoods as well indicates that they were constructed to almost the same extent as the Safranbolu dwellings found in Bursa and the Cumalıkızık houses in Samsun. In addition to this, all of the houses in question in Bursa and Samsun have been taken under protection and included in the UNESCO heritage list. We are of the opinion that all of the Eski Gediz houses, which are the subject of our research, should be restored and, furthermore, should be included in the UNESCO heritage list.

Figure 7. Mansion-Type House Reflecting Traditional Ottoman Architecture

3.2. Modern Dwellings

Another housing type found in the region consists of modern ones constructed entirely with contemporary building materials using present-day capabilities, which do not clearly reflect the influence of the environment (Özav, 2002, p. 37). This type of building form, which is not high in number, is generally composed of dwellings where materials are procured from a distance and purchased ready-made, such as brick, tile, iron, cement, and lime (Figure 9). When evaluated from this perspective, both housing types and settlement forms can be shaped by transportation routes, which leads to the idea that transportation networks have an influence settlement patterns (Yasak, 2018, p. 2707). Families residing in modern dwellings have constructed the roofs of their houses with a two-sided slope (gable roof). Families have installed solar energy systems on their roofs to meet their hot water needs.

Figure 8. An Example of a Modern Housing in Sabirgazi Neighborhood

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, the research area is situated in a relatively isolated location between Kütahya and Uşak. Furthermore, the fact that economic activities consist only of sub-branches of the agricultural sector and partially of the service sector is considered a disadvantage. It was determined during oral interviews that most of the townspeople who abandoned their homes after the Great Gediz Earthquake did not return. The vast majority of the population migrated to New Gediz after the 1970 earthquake. The continued existence of wooden dwellings in the town, which bear the traces of many civilizations, indicates that the town holds significant importance for tourism. Moreover, the completion of restoration works will accelerate tourism momentum. Finally, it is necessary to highlight the pension (guesthouse) and hotel potentials of the area, similar to examples such as "Birgi Houses, Cumalıkızık, and Safranbolu Houses," of which there are many examples in our country.

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